

Replication Package

Microservices Development in Hybrid Applications: A Bibliographic Review

Submitted to SBES 2026 — Track on Innovative Ideas and Emerging Results (IIER)

Research Questions

ID	Question
RQ1	Which technologies and approaches have been used for microservices development in hybrid applications?
RQ2	Which architectures and methods are employed in building microservices-based applications?
RQ3	Which programming languages, tools, or frameworks are most commonly used in this context?

Search Protocol

Databases: SBC OpenLib · Google Scholar · IEEE Xplore · ACM Digital Library · Scopus

Publication period: 2022–2026

Search strings:

- PT: (microserviços OR serviços) AND desenvolvimento AND "aplicações híbridas"
- EN: (microservices OR services) AND development AND "hybrid applications"

Inclusion Criteria

ID	Criterion
IC1	Published between 2022 and 2026
IC2	Primary study
IC3	Addresses technologies, methods, or tools for microservices development
IC4	Full text available in the searched database

Exclusion Criteria

ID	Criterion
EC1	Duplicate across databases
EC2	Outside the defined publication period
EC3	Does not address microservices or services development
EC4	Full text not accessible

Selected Studies (E1–E20)

ID	Title	Year	Source
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E1	MoocFlix: A Microservices-Based Architecture for Scalable and Efficient MOOC Streaming Platforms	2025	IEEE
E2	An Intelligent Hybrid Mobile Application Architecture Integrating Cloud Based Generative AI Services	2025	Google Scholar
E3	Dynamic Analysis for Detecting Microservices Antipatterns	2025	SBC
E4	Modernização de Arquitetura de Sistemas: Uma abordagem para transformação digital no sistema financeiro	2024	SBC
E5	SP2Mic: Uma ferramenta para geração de código de microsserviços a partir de stored procedures	2024	SBC
E6	JS-Distributor: Decomposing Monolith Applications into Microservices	2025	SBC
E7	Processo de Migração de Aplicação Mainframe Cobol para Microsserviços Java na Nuvem	2024	SBC
E8	Distributed Healthcare Information System Based on High-Concurrency Microservice Architecture	2023	IEEE
E9	RM2MS: A Tool for Automatic Identification of Microservices from Requirements Models	2023	IEEE
E10	Migration of Monolithic Systems to Microservices using AI: A Systematic Mapping Study	2024	SBC
E11	A Real-time Data Synchronization Approach for High-availability Micro Applications	2025	SBC
E12	SPL Integrated with Microservices: A Hybrid Architectural Proposal for Multitenant SaaS	2023	SBC
E13	Agentic AI for Microservices: Autonomous Optimization of High-Volume Financial Transactions in Cloud Native Environments	2025	IEEE
E14	M2FaaS: Transparent and Fault Tolerant FaaSification of Node.js Monolith Code Blocks	2022	Scopus
E15	Plataforma SobreVidas: Solução Tecnológica para o Rastreamento e Monitoramento Contínuo na APS	2024	SBC
E16	An Efficient Microservices Architecture for MLOps	2023	IEEE
E17	Towards Migrating Legacy Software Systems to Microservice-based Architectures	2022	IEEE
E18	Implementing a PHP API Gateway Based on Microservices Architecture	2024	IEEE
E19	RapidMS: A Tool for Supporting Rapid Microservices Generation and Refinement from Requirements Model	2023	IEEE
E20	Low-Coupling and High-Cohesion Microservice Partitioning Method to Support Rapid Development of Steel Industry Management Systems	2024	IEEE

Extraction Results — RQ1: Technologies and Concepts

Technology / Concept	Studies
Microservices Architecture	E1–E9, E12, E13, E15, E16, E19
Cloud-Native / Distributed Systems	E1, E3, E4, E8, E13, E16
Cloud Computing / Serverless	E2, E7, E13, E14
Containerization (Docker)	E1, E4, E6, E15
Orchestration (Kubernetes)	E1, E3, E4, E13
Message Brokers (Kafka / RabbitMQ)	E1, E4, E6, E8, E11, E15
API Gateway	E2, E5, E12, E15, E16, E18
AI / Machine Learning	E2, E7, E9, E10, E13, E15
Generative AI (GenAI)	E2, E7, E13, E15
Domain-Driven Design (DDD)	E12, E19, E20
CI/CD and DevOps	E3, E4, E16
Model-Driven Engineering	E9, E19
FaaS / Serverless Functions	E14

Extraction Results — RQ2: Research Methods

Method	Count	Studies
Experimental / with evaluation	9	E1, E3, E5, E6, E7, E8, E13, E18, E19
Architectural Proposal	8	E2, E9, E11, E12, E15, E16, E19, E20
Case Study	5	E9, E12, E17, E19, E20
ML / Evolutionary Algorithms	4	E9, E10, E13, E17

Extraction Results — RQ3: Programming Languages and Tools

Language / Framework	Count	Studies
Java / Spring Boot	10	E1, E5–E9, E11, E17, E19, E20
JavaScript / Node.js / TypeScript	6	E1, E4, E6, E11, E14, E15
Python	3	E3, E4, E13
C# / .NET	2	E4, E5
Kotlin	1	E15
PHP	1	E18
Dart (Flutter)	1	E2
UML / OCL (model-driven)	2	E9, E19

Generative AI Usage

Study	Tool / Approach
E2	LLMs for text and image generation via cloud-based GenAI services
E7	ChatGPT for automatic COBOL→Java transpilation
E13	Agentic AI with Deep Q-Network (DQN) for autonomous optimization
E15	LLMs + Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) for clinical decision support

Study Context

Context	Studies
Academic	E1, E3, E4, E6, E7, E8, E9, E10, E12, E13, E14, E15, E16, E17, E18, E19, E20
Academic + Industry partnership	E5, E11
Corporate	E2

Artifact Availability

All selected studies were retrieved from publicly accessible databases. The extraction protocol, inclusion/exclusion criteria, and classification data are intended to support transparency and reproducibility of the results. Requests for additional information can be directed to the authors via the paper submission system.